

PRACTICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC COMPETENCE IN FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM

F.T. Rabbimova¹, U.N. Usanov²,

V. Jamolova³, M. To'ychiyeva⁴

¹⁻²⁻³⁻⁴Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute

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is to improve the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers.

ABSTRACT

illuminating the pedagogical-psychological features and factors of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers;

identifying the content and essence of the components of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers;

identifying the stages and didactic parameters of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers;

developing the interdisciplinary modular education technology of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers.

The object of the research was the process of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers.

Scientific novelty of the research are as follows:

An effective component of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers has been identified by the combination of the pedagogical process with artistic-aesthetic activity, and the ability to acquire functional and systematic decision-making skills in the design of artistic-aesthetic activities;

The stages of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers have been developed on the basis of the principles of increasing the artistic-aesthetic effectiveness of the study material and ensuring the interdisciplinary interaction and integration in the content of education;

The interdisciplinary modular technology of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers has been developed within specific subjects and sciences (block-modular), and on the basis of ensuring the interdisciplinary integration;

The resultative criterion for improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers has been determined by educational (enrichment of artistic-aesthetic activities), normative (setting axiological consciousness for environmental protection in students) and practical (students' environmental protection, research and labour activities) indicators.

The reliability of the research results is explained by the fact that the used approaches, methods and theoretical data were derived from official sources, the effectiveness of the analyses and

experimental studies was based on mathematical statistical methods, conclusions, recommendations and proposals were implemented in practice, and the obtained results were confirmed by competent structures.

Implementation of the research results.

Based on the obtained scientific results on the improvement of the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers:

Pedagogical-psychological features and factors of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers have been incorporated in the content of the State Educational Standards in Bachelor's Degrees that were approved by the Resolution No.2-540 of "O'zstandart" Agency of 15 February 2015. As a result, conditions will be created for the development of artistic-aesthetic competence.

The proposals on practical introduction of interdisciplinary modular education technology for improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers were used in developing educational and normative materials in accordance with the Resolution No.242 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 20 August 2015 "On Measures for the Retraining and Professional Development of Leading and Pedagogical Staff of Higher Education Institutions" and the Resolution No.103 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 27 February 2017 "On Amendments and Additions Introduced in the Charter of Courses for Retraining and Professional Development of Leading and Pedagogical Staff of Higher Education Institutions" and the state requirements and curriculum programs approved by the Decree No.3 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary

Special Education of 8 August 2016 "On the Methodology of Teaching of Exact and Natural Sciences (Biology)";

The proposals for the development of didactic provision of improving the artistic-aesthetic competence in future teachers were used in working out the technology for the development of artistic-aesthetic competence and development of ecological thinking in the future ecologists in accordance with Paragraph 3 of the State Grant for the "Development of Ecotourism" (Certificate No.26-09) allocated by the Fund for Nongovernmental Non-profit Organizations and Other Civil Society Institutions under the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

A model for the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers

Both empirical and theoretical methods are widely used in pedagogical and psychological research. As V. Zagvyazinsky noted, the empirical methods of research can not be opposed to the theoretical methods that serve to reveal the essence of the origin of the studied voelik, its internal structure, sources, development mechanisms and functions ". In fact, they complement each other and serve to ensure the reliability of the research results. Theoretical methods of research allow to understand the hidden laws in the evidence, to obtain general, necessary, important aspects, to understand the interaction of developmental factors. Theoretical methods of research can include analysis, synthesis, abstraction, and concretization. One of the special methods related to the theoretical level of pedagogical research is modeling.

"Modeling serves to reflect a holistic range of research activities. The researcher

carefully examines the essence of the series. After all, it enriches the theory with conclusions and ideas as a final model. Thus, modeling allows you to visualize the selected object in the form of a series".

The term "model" should describe a system (sample, template), reflect its specific properties, its relationship with another, so-called real system, and in a sense replace it.

The concept of "model" is used in many fields of science. A model is an artificially created object in the form of a scheme, physical constructions, definite shapes and formulas, which is similar to the object under study, its structure, properties, interactions and relationships between the elements of the object in a simple and clear way.

A model is a symbolically created object that is similar to the object under study in the form of a picture, table, diagram, etc., and reflects and demonstrates the structure, properties, interactions and relationships between its elements in a simple, condensed form.

Modeling is a method of studying objects of different nature in order to determine or determine the properties of an existing object or objects being reconstructed on the basis of their analogues.

As can be seen from the above definitions, modeling allows for a deeper and more complete study of the manifestations of relationships and patterns in many real objects and requires the abstraction of all elements pertaining to the system.

In the process of implementing the pedagogical process, it is difficult to establish a legal relationship between complex, multifaceted and diverse factors. That is why it is important to create a

theoretical model of the pedagogical process.

In pedagogy, modeling is effectively used in solving important didactic tasks, such as optimizing the structure of the educational process, increasing the independent learning activity of students, the implementation of a person-centered approach in the learning process. Of course, in pedagogical research there is a special need for a theoretical model. To develop a theoretical model, the object is usually considered as an integral system that requires the study of components, elements, subsystems separately. The components of the system are interconnected, as well as structural relationships that serve to solve specific tasks.

Systematic, person-centered, activity-oriented and competent approaches serve as a methodological basis for the model of development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers.

A system is a collection of interacting objects conditioned not only by its unique properties, but also by its new integrative qualities. The system itself reflects the following characteristics: the presence of a structure, ie a clear connection and relationship between the elements; the presence of integrative quality (systemic); purposefulness; the presence of communicative features.

According to T. Shamova, the system is a purposeful unity of interconnected elements with a new integrative quality, denying the individuality of each; integrity associated with the external environment.

According to N.Muslimov, the system (Greek systema - integral, consisting of parts, attached) means a certain integrity,

unity, interaction and many elements that are interconnected.

A system is a whole that represents the unity of parts that are arranged in an orderly fashion and are interconnected. A system is a whole that represents the unity of parts that are arranged in an orderly fashion and are interconnected. A "system" is a set of elements arranged in a specific order, which, in an interconnected state, form a certain integral unit.

From the definitions of the concept of "system", it can be concluded that the concept of "systemicity" can reflect the fact that processes and events can form a system, the existence of the system, the systemic structure of the material world and its forms of knowledge.

The systematic approach is a direction of scientific knowledge and methodology of social practice, which is based on the perception of objects as a system. This requires imagining the object as a whole, as a whole, according to the content and essence of its connections and means. In the study of the object of study, it is divided into several parts with separate features, and the interrelated and interdependent features between them are identified, because each part has its own impact on the change of the whole system.

The person-centered approach in pedagogy means that the individual is focused on the organization and implementation of the pedagogical process as the main criterion for the purpose, subject, outcome and effectiveness of the educational process.

In modern psychological and pedagogical publications, information on the integrated activities of the selected approaches, which are selected separately from the individual approach to education, is widely covered. However, this approach is a much

narrower concept than the self-directed approach, in which all human activities and behaviors are overlooked.

In the person-activity-oriented approach, the components of the person and the activity are closely related to each other, because in the process of this approach the person acts as a subject and, in turn, determines the development of the person as a subject under the influence of various factors. As V. Slasten points out, activity serves as the main tool and condition of personal development, more precisely, in pedagogy the person-centered approach is interrelated with the activity-oriented approach. From the point of view of the scientist, it is understood that any activity has its own psychological structure: motive, purpose, action, condition, means and result. Based on this rule, it should be noted that the implementation of an activity-oriented approach does not take into account the specifics of the individual as a subject, the teacher may ignore the main aspects of the organization of students' learning activities.

Of course, the student effectively masters the content of education in the presence of an internal need for this process and active positive motivation.

A competent approach to education is characterized by the ability to enhance the pragmatic and humane orientation of the teaching process, as described in the previous chapter of the study. Also, the competent approach is aimed primarily at a new approach to defining the goals and outcomes of biological education, has its own specific requirements and requires reconsideration of components of the educational process, such as content, pedagogical technology, monitoring and evaluation tools.

As a necessary condition for creating a model of a pedagogical process, it is necessary to clearly define its components. More precisely, the pedagogical process requires the unity and interdependence of goal-oriented, content-based, organizational-activity and analytical-result components.

In the course of the research, a model for the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in biology teachers was developed based on blocks to clarify the purpose, selection of teaching materials, organizational and operational, evaluation, definition of expected results (Table 2.1.1).

This model has the appearance of an open system, based on the didactic parameters of the organization of biological education, which allows to make changes and additions to its blocks and content.

The first block of the model reflects the goals and objectives of developing artistic and aesthetic competence in biology teachers. The content of this block covers the social order of the state and society to train specialists capable of organizing creative, artistic and aesthetic activities,

taking into account the qualification requirements of the Action Plan for Higher Education Development 2017-2021, "Methods of teaching biology."

The block also reflected the following tasks necessary to achieve the set goal: to form the need and desire for artistic and aesthetic activities; interest in the profession of biology teacher and the desire to pursue this profession; acquisition of professional knowledge, skills and abilities; laws and principles of designing artistic and aesthetic activities in the process of biological education; acquisition of knowledge of methods and techniques; solving problems related to the process of biological education based on conceptual and creative approaches, the formation of the ability to develop tasks of artistic and aesthetic nature; to develop the ability to independently organize the process of working on tasks of artistic and aesthetic nature; mastering the methods of organizing the educational process on the basis of materials of artistic and aesthetic content.

(Table 2.1.1).

Theoretical model of development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers

Goal Clarification Block			
Social order		Qualification description	Qualification requirements
Purpose	Development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers		
Duties	Formation of positive motivation for professional activity	Formation of professional knowledge and skills	Practical work experience
Training materials selection block			
Competence components	Motivational	Cognitive	About the activity

Educational sciences	"Methods of teaching biology" and "Solving problems and exercises in biology" and "Technology and design of teaching biology"		
Didactic material	Educational-methodical complexes, methodical manuals and recommendations		
Organizational activity block			
Type of activity	Educational and professional		
Form of organization of education	Problem speech, visual speech, interactive speech	Heuristic and reflexive seminar	Creative work
Teaching methods	Problem-solving, logical, independent work and interactive methods		
Evaluation criteria block			
Criteria	Motivational	Cognitive	About the activity
Indicators	Need, passion, interest in artistic and aesthetic activities	Theoretical knowledge and methods of artistic and aesthetic activity	Stages, methods and techniques of designing artistic and aesthetic activities
Levels	Low	Medium	High
Block of determination of expected results			
Interval	Formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of future biology teachers in artistic and aesthetic activities		
Final	Deciding on artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers		

The block of selection of teaching materials of the block of development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers provides for the definition of the content of education on the basis of a person-centered approach. This process is carried out in the framework of the disciplines "Methods of teaching biology", "Solving problems and exercises in biology", "Technology and design of teaching biology" and requires attention to the following aspects: identification of artistic and aesthetic aspects of the study material; ensuring interdisciplinary relevance in the context of biological education and relying on the principle of integration; to provide students with creative, problem-solving tasks that stimulate not only theoretical, but also

artistic and figurative thinking; formation of cognitive (cognitive) problems on the basis of emotional, personal significance. Selecting the content of biological education on the basis of a person-centered approach requires the future teacher to determine his place in four important areas: man, society, nature, noosphere (field of mind). The field of "Human" requires understanding that human life itself is a value, individuality, the specificity of the process, the content of activities, the peak of human development. Defining one's place in the sphere of "society" occurs through the acquisition of values in the form of homeland, people's power, democracy, transparency, the rule of law, family, labor, civic responsibility; It can be organized by defining one's place in the

field of "nature", understanding oneself as a part of nature and improving oneself in accordance with nature (health, aesthetic basis, spiritual desire). It also implies having an ecological culture, an understanding of the sense of responsibility to future generations in the process of mastering and changing nature. Understanding the moral responsibility of using the products of scientific and technological development as a field of "noosphere" (the field of mind), to form an idea of the consequences of human inadequacy when working with technology, to master the world of spiritual culture with all its diversity that is, the formation of a civic attitude to the historical, spiritual, moral struggle of the people, the preservation and restoration of cultural monuments, the re-creation of national traditions and their development as part of the world of material and spiritual culture. The next block of development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers is called organizational-activity-oriented. The teaching process "takes place in the unity of teaching and learning". In this block, we have reflected the activities of both faculty and students.

The basis of student activity in higher education is the learning process. It is in the process of training that the main goal of training is realized. It has a rapid impact on the development and characteristics of mental processes in the student, as well as the acquisition of professional knowledge, skills and abilities.

The model also reflects the professional training of students as a type of educational activity. As A. Verbitsky noted, from the point of view of contextual education, the combination of elements of both educational and future pedagogical activity

is modeled as the main type of educational activity of students in the classroom.

This is the scientific, socio-psychological content of the future teacher's professional activity, which allows to look at his work as a whole.

The effectiveness of the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future teachers of biology requires the choice of forms, methods and means of teaching the subject "Methods of teaching biology" in accordance with the objectives.

The fourth block of the model is called the assessment criteria, which reflects the definition of criteria, indicators and levels of mastery of the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers. It reflects the motivational, cognitive and activity criteria for the development of artistic and aesthetic competence.

Motivational criteria reflect the emotional state of the person in relation to future professional activity, serve to determine the motivation for the acquisition of professional knowledge and professional formation. This criterion includes the following indicators: the need and passion for artistic and aesthetic activities; striving to become a biology teacher; striving to acquire professional knowledge, skills and competencies.

Cognitive criteria are characterized by the acquisition of professional knowledge in the field of artistic and aesthetic activity in the process of biological education. Laws and principles of designing objects of artistic and aesthetic activity on the indicators of cognitive criteria; acquisition of knowledge of methods and techniques.

Criteria for the activity reflect the ability to carry out professional activities, to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, to

master the methods of designing artistic and aesthetic activities. To develop the ability to independently organize the process of working on tasks of artistic and aesthetic nature of the performance indicators; mastering the methods of organizing the educational process on the basis of materials of artistic and aesthetic content.

Assessment criteria allow to diagnose and correct the level of development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers at all stages of education.

The block of determining the expected results of the presented model serves to determine the appropriateness of the intermediate and final results of the development of artistic and aesthetic competence in future biology teachers.

References:

1. Раббимова Ф.Т. Бўлажак ўқитувчилар – соғлом авлод тарбиячилари.// Ўзбекистонда соғлом авлодни шакллантиришнинг ижтимоий, педагогик-психологик асослари. Республика илмий-амалий анжумани материаллари. – Т., 2014. – Б. 239-241.
2. Раббимова Ф.Т. Табиатшунослик фанларини ўқитишда Шарқ алломаларининг фикрларидан фойдаланиш. - Ж. Биология, 2009. – Б.230-233.
3. Раббимова Ф.Т. Талабаларни эстетик тарбиялаш.//Формирование гармонично развитого поколения в современных условиях.-№8. Тошкент, 2012. – Б.85-88.
4. Раббимова Ф.Т. Training of future biology teachers to process of learning aesthetics of native nature // The advanced science open access journal. Desember 2015 у USA. -100-101 p.
5. Раббимова Ф.Т. Воспитание и развитие учащихся VI-VII классов в процессе обучения. Ж. Молодой ученый. - №2. –Москва, 2014.с.840-843
6. Раббимова Ф.Т. Олий ўқув юрти ва мактабдаги таълимнинг мазмуни, унинг табиатни эстетик билишдаги имкониятлари.// “Инновацион ғоялар, технологиялар ва лойиҳаларни ишлаб чиқаришга татбиқ этиш муаммолари” мавзусидаги IV Республика илмий техник конференцияси материаллари. -№5. Тошкент, 2012. – Б.288-289.
7. Раббимова Ф.Т. Табиат эстетикасини билишга бўлғуси ўқитувчиларни тайёрлаш методикаси.// Гармонично развитое поколение – условие стабильного развития благополучия и процветания общества. –Тошкент, 2013. -№9. – Б. 202-208.
8. Раббимова Ф.Т. Биологиядан дарсдан ташқари ишларни ташкил этиш.// “Фан ва амалиёт” мажмуасининг долзарб муаммолари. -№8. –Тошкент, 2013. – Б.327-330.
9. Раббимова Ф.Т. Табиат эстетикасини билишга бўлғуси ўқитувчиларни тайёрлаш методикаси.// Гармонично развитое поколение – условие стабильного развития благополучия и процветания общества. -№9. –Тошкент, 2013. – Б.202-208.
10. Раббимова Ф.Т. Биология таълимида интеллектуал ўйинлардан фойдаланиш.// Гармонично развитое поколение – условие стабильного развития благополучия и процветания общества. - №9. –Тошкент, 2013. – Б. 209-216.
11. Раббимова Ф.Т. Табиатшунослик фанларини ўқитишда V-VIII синфларда эстетик тарбия.// The advanced science open access journal. – №12. -Desember 2013/101-103

12. Раббимова Ф.Т. Зирадошлар оиласи мавзусидаги дарсинг таълим технологияси // Республика илмий-амалий конференцияси материаллари. -2014 (16-17 апрель).
13. Раббимова Ф.Т. Биология ўқув жараёнига таълим технологияларини жорий этишнинг долзарблиги. // Соғлом бола – жамиятнинг мустаҳкам
14. Раббимова Ф.Т., Қаршибоева Н.Х. Биология ўқитиш методикаси. // Ўқув қўлланма. -2021.152 Б.
15. Раббимова Ф.Т., Азимова Д.Э. Бўлажак биология ўқитувчиларида бадиий-эстетик компетентликни ривожлантириш технологияси. // Монография. -2021.152 Б.